

Speculation on $\Delta E \Delta t \geq \frac{1}{2} \hbar$, Retarded Time and a Charge at Rest

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In quantum mechanics, the use of Heisenberg's uncertainty relationship $\Delta E \Delta t \geq \frac{1}{2} \hbar$ to qualitatively describe virtual particles in forces is well-known. (1) In 1898 and 1890, Lienard and Wiechart made use of retarded time (2)(3) when solving the problem of a moving/accelerating charge. At first, these two ideas seem separate.

We try to argue here, however, that the two should be related, at least qualitatively. We consider the case of a charge at rest and argue that signals moving at the speed of c should travel from the charge Q at the origin to a point r , but should also move back. These signals would seem to be linked to energy and momentum, but do not seem to obey Newtonian mechanics. In other words, there seem to be energy fluctuations and energy may disappear from near the charge, move at speed c to some point and then disappear there and move back to the origin. These fluctuations seem to already exist in the case of a charge at rest, but are developed in more detail for an accelerating charge in (4). As a result, we argue that retarded time in electromagnetism is linked with quantum energy fluctuations. We note that the use of a retarded time is consistent with special relativity and so argue that special relativity and quantum mechanics are directly linked.

Quantum Force and $\Delta E \Delta t \geq \frac{1}{2} \hbar$

It is known in quantum mechanics that interactions between particles may occur through the exchange of virtual particles which are linked to Heisenberg's uncertainty relationship:

$$\Delta E \Delta t \geq \frac{1}{2} \hbar \quad ((1))$$

In a qualitative sense, energy may disappear from one place and appear at another provided that this loss of energy does not last for a time of more than Δt . This is a purely quantum effect, but we try to argue that it seems to be present qualitatively in the retarded time approach of electromagnetism, even for a charge at rest.

Retarded Time and Electromagnetism

The notion of retarded time in electromagnetism was developed independently by Lienard (1898) and Wiechart (1900) for a moving charge. The idea is that if the electrostatic potential is measured at a position r from a fixed origin at time t , then a signal must have come from a piece of charge at position r' at t' . At time t , this piece of charge is at a new position r'' . In other words, the potential at r, t sees the effect of the charge at an earlier time, not at t , because a signal moves at speed c (speed of light in a vacuum) and not instantaneously. Formally, retarded time is given by (3):

$$t - R/c \quad \text{where } R = |r - r'| \quad ((2))$$

where r vector is taken from a fixed origin to the measurement point and r' from the same origin to a piece of charge.

We note that retarded time is used to describe a moving/accelerating charge ((3)) p458. We suggest, however, that the idea should also apply for a charge at rest and argue that this leads to some consequences related to energy fluctuation, i.e. a quantum mechanical-like viewpoint.

Charge at Rest

A charge Q at rest at the origin does not change in time, on average. According to the concept of retarded time, a measurement at r vector, t sense the result of the charge at an earlier place and time (the retarded time) because a signal, moving at c , is sent at this time. Given that charge is at rest, this does not seem like much of an issue. It seems that signals are being sent continuously from the charge. These arrive at r vector at different times (also in the case of motion). The question we ask is: What happens to these signals? Given that they travel at speed c , it seems they are associated with energy and momentum. A measurement at r vector, t , however, is only linked with one signal, not with all past signals. Thus, a single signal arrives at r vector and then disappears or travels back to the charge. In other words, there is no reason for signals not be moving back and forth, even though there is no physical reflection present. As a result, there seems to be a kind of periodic process occurring with energy associated with a signal disappearing for a time as it moves to a point r vector and then back (without any physical reflection). This unusual non-Newtonian behaviour (it seems) occurs in a classical electromagnetic system and seems to be akin to Heisenberg's energy uncertainty principle, i.e. a quantum phenomenon. In fact, performing a qualitative calculation one may consider that the potential energy at r vector is proportional to $1/|r \text{ vector}|$. A photon of this energy is represented by $h\bar{\nu}$ wavelength and it takes: $\text{wavelength} = c \Delta t$ for this photon to arrive at the measurement point. This yields:

$$\Delta E \Delta t = h\bar{\nu} \quad ((3))$$

where ΔE is the energy temporarily lost from near the charge Q .

Thus, we argue that a quantum mechanical type of energy fluctuations must occur in a classical scenario associated with a retarded time.

We note that the idea of a signal being sent from a charge arriving at a point r vector and then disappearing or returning should also hold for a moving charge. The situation, however, seems to be more complicated because a measurement at r vector (using presumably a test charge) feels the effects of a moving charge at a past time. This same test charge, however, may also send a signal to the moving charge, but this would also have to be done in the past. Thus, it seems that signals are continuously being sent forwards and backwards leading to energy fluctuations in a system.

Moving/Accelerating Charge

Although the above statements are of a qualitative nature, (4) investigates them in more detail by considering equations of motion with forces and argues that $F = qE + qv \times B$ represents an average and that the Heisenberg energy uncertainty principle is at work in an accelerating system. (4) focuses on terms, proportional to acceleration, which arise in force equations (for an accelerating charge) and inconsistencies which seem to arise unless one considers energy fluctuations (a quantum idea) in a classical system. We argue that these issues seem to be present in the case of a charge at rest if one uses the concept of retarded time.

Connection with Special Relativity

The use of retarded time is consistent with special relativistic results. Thus, retarded time leads to the quantum idea of energy fluctuations and at the same time is equivalent to relativistic results. We suggest this means there exists a strong association between special relativity and quantum mechanics which we have argued for in previous notes. In particular, we argued that the Lorentz invariant: $-Et + px$ has the same value if $x \rightarrow x + C/p$ and $t \rightarrow t + C/E$ where C is a constant. This leads to the idea of periodic fluctuations if one considers an eigenfunction equation for E and p linked with the operator id/dt partial and $-id/dx$ partial. The eigenfunction is $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$. Here we argue in the opposite direction, seeing quantum fluctuations first from retarded time and then noting that retarded time is consistent with special relativity.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the idea of virtual particles, associated with Heisenberg's energy uncertainty relationship, being used to facilitate interactions between particles leads to the notion of energy fluctuations, i.e. energy disappearing from one place for a short time before reappearing.

We suggest that a similar idea seems to be linked with the notion of retarded time in electromagnetism. Retarded time is usually applied to moving/accelerating charge systems, but we argue it should apply to a charge at rest. It seems that signals (linked with energy/momentum) are continuously being sent from the charge to various measurement points. If a measurement occurs at time t , it only senses one signal, so we suggest that the signals which arrived earlier return to the charge. This is like reflection with no reflection source, i.e. an usual non-Newtonian energy fluctuation. Thus, the system is full of energy fluctuations and the smooth equations of electromagnetism are averages. This is a quantum mechanical viewpoint which occurs in a classical electromagnetic problem.

Furthermore, we note that the notion of retarded time is consistent with special relativity. Thus, we argue for a strong connection between quantum mechanics and special relativity. We have made this argument before for the Lorentz invariant $-Et + px$ by noting that it remains constant for $t \rightarrow t + C/E$ and $x \rightarrow x + C/p$. One may create a periodic eigenfunction for id/dt partial and $-id/dx$ partial, namely $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$. In other words, special relativity is consistent with such a periodic complex probability. This quantum scenario ultimately becomes associated with the Heisenberg uncertainty principle.

References

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